

DELTA: DLT-Database Synchronization

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Abstract—An increasingly common application for DLTs is their exploitation in enterprise systems operated by a consortium of organizations, who may assume different roles and whose interaction takes place over a blockchain network (in this scope, often permissioned), which holds a data state that they need to query frequently. In this regard, one of the main drawbacks of DLTs is their unsuitability for the efficient execution of complex queries on the data stored by the nodes comprising the network.

Arising from this issue, many solutions propose to dump the ledger contents into databases, which, due to their own nature and purpose, are certainly optimized for the execution of such queries. However, most proposals on this area are not intended for querying the shared state held by the network, just the transaction history. Actually, through conducting a study on the state of the art, a lack of support for handling and querying complex structured data has been identified.

DELTA provides a solution for the synchronization, with negligible overload, of the state of a DLT into a database, enabling (a) the operation with smart contracts whose data possess a complex structure and (b) the efficient execution of elaborate queries on these data. By using DELTA, query times decrease, at least, between one and five orders of magnitude, depending on the DLT, compared to queries directed to the ledger nodes.

Index Terms—Blockchain, DLT, ledger, database.

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last decade, Distributed Ledger Technologies (e.g., Blockchain) have been regarded as disruptive technologies, mainly owing its popularity to its usage in cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin [1] and Ethereum [2]. This disruptiveness generated, altogether, an enormous hype around the technology, enthusiasm about applying it to a variety of use cases and, inevitably, misconceptions and inappropriate applications. One of these inappropriate uses was employing blockchains as a storage technology and trying to exploit them as databases [3].

DLTs have several well known advantages, such as immutability, non-repudiation, transparency, high availability or helping to avoid intermediaries, among others [4]. However, most DLT implementations also hold some disadvantages, one of the most prominent of them being their unsuitability to efficiently perform complex queries on the shared data state stored by the nodes composing the network. Although DLTs are not conceived as databases, this does not vanish the fact that sometimes retrieving information from them becomes

necessary [5]. Even in platforms that allow to perform queries on the state, e.g., Hyperledger Fabric (HLF), assets are usually serialized and stored in key-value databases, which causes the efficient execution of these queries to not be feasible in case the data possess a complex structure. This is troublesome, given the increasingly common adoption of the Blockchain technology in enterprise-grade applications [6], whose state usually has such complex structure and demands those efficient and elaborate queries.

This increasing usage raises a second issue, the inherent complexity of DLTs. The interaction with DLT platforms is usually cumbersome for developers, especially when compared to the operation with traditional databases. Thus, we believe there is a need to offer DLT users and developers a tool that simplifies the interaction with the DLT, abstracting them from the underlying technology while, at the same time, it provides mechanisms for the efficient execution of complex queries.

On this line we present DELTA: a solution for transferring the data of a DLT to a database and keeping their contents synchronized. With DELTA, we intend to ease the execution of read operations on the DLT. Once transactions are committed on the DLT, they will be updated in the database, making the result of changes on the ledger’s data to be readable. This way, we offer a friendly and powerful interface for the efficient execution of potentially complex read operations, which is no other than that of the database without losing the virtues of DLTs, which remain as an immutable ledger that can be audited at any moment. Our main contributions are:

- A driver-based solution capable of synchronizing DLTs into databases enabling the efficient execution of complex queries on the data stored in the DLT. This synchronization is based on a purposely designed event specification and, similarly, fault tolerance mechanisms have been implemented for resilience.
- Drivers for two DLTs, HLF and Quorum, and for a NoSQL database, MongoDB. Note that Quorum is an Ethereum-compatible permissioned blockchain. Thus, what is mentioned in regard to Quorum is easily portable to Ethereum and other Ethereum-based blockchains.
- Base smart contracts implementing event emission for write operations, for HLF and Quorum.

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The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents a study of the state of the art on DLT synchronization into databases. Section III provides an overview on DELTA, while Section IV conducts an analysis of DELTA’s high-level design, and describes its most remarkable features. Section V compares two DLT implementations -HLF & Quorum- using MongoDB in terms of throughput and performance. Section VI discusses the premises and limitations of the solution provided and, finally, Section VII provides some conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

Most publications [7]–[16] and tools [17]–[20] interested in efficiently querying DLTs focus on obtaining information about the transaction history, the blocks or the DLT accounts. Many of them synchronize the DLT contents into databases. To do so, they use a fixed data model that either may be completely dependant on the chosen DLT or may propose a more abstract and general design that intends to be compatible with the most common technologies (e.g., Bitcoin and Ethereum in public networks, or HLF in permissioned ones). However, they are unlikely to pay further attention to the management of the state data held by the ledger, which they usually store in raw text format within a single field that is bound to the corresponding transaction. This makes it easier to execute queries on the transaction history, but stands in the way of analyzing the shared state itself. Some examples of this approach are `ether_sql` [18] (synchronization of an Ethereum network over a relational database) and the integration of Azure’s blockchain service with its CosmosDB [17] database.

This approach makes sense in the Bitcoin network, whose transaction logic is limited to the transfer of units of the currency between accounts. Here we find tools such as `bitcoina-be` [19] and `blockchainSQL` [20]. In addition, datasets that contain a dump of the transaction history of various cryptocurrencies have been stored in Google’s Big Query database [21], leveraging its support for collections as the data type of a single column as well as the computing capabilities available through Google’s own cloud infrastructure.

However, in DLTs with Turing complete smart contract execution engines, e.g., Ethereum and HLF, the structure of the state data stored in the ledger may be complex. An increasingly common application of these networks consists in their integration as enterprise-grade systems, operated by a consortium, keeping a shared state that is updated by means of the transactional execution of smart contracts into which their business processes are codified [6]. Here, the DLT network is a priceless audit mechanism providing immutability and non-repudiation guarantees to the data emitted in transactions [4]. Even so, during the normal operation of these systems, what is usually required is not to query the transaction history, but the efficient execution of queries over the stored state [22].

Proposals regarding the ability to launch efficient queries on the state data of a DLT can be split into two broad approaches. Within a first approach, we can find those proposals that build a distributed database assimilating the cryptographic mechanisms of a DLT, combining the security warranties provided

by the DLT with the high efficiency to execute complex queries on the data stored within the database. This approach is followed by BigchainDB [23] (on top of MongoDB), Blockchain Relational Database [24] (on top of PostgreSQL) and ChainifyDB [25] (on top of PostgreSQL or MySQL). The second approach includes those proposals that dump a snapshot of the current state stored by the DLT network into a database through the connection to a node that hosts a replica of the ledger, keeping the database synchronized with the ledger state whenever new transactions are committed at the node. Proposals within this latter approach can themselves be classified attending to different aspects of their design.

a) **The complexity level in the structure of state data.** LedgerSync [26] (HL Sawtooth) and Vent [27] (HL Burrow) allow to synchronize the state of a peer node into a relational database, but they do not support nested data types in the definition of this state (stored as JSONs by the DLT’s internal key-value database), which implies that each document type would be stored into a different single table. This is an important limitation, since the DLT state is unlikely to stick to this restriction and, moreover, the true potential of relational databases regarding the modelling of the relationships between associated entity types is not being exploited. Ledgerdata Refiner [28] (HLF) and ChainSQL [29], [30] (Ripple) also synchronize the state data of a peer node into a relational database, allowing the structure of the state to be more complex than previous options and including nested elements. However, both of them display important disadvantages. Ledgerdata Refiner includes an interesting mechanism that performs an inference of the data schema, but, as the state is still stored as raw text, it makes the system inefficient for the execution of queries on it (even if they are allowed). ChainSQL’s design proposal turns out to be too invasive, since every interaction with both the peer node and the database must be performed through their middleware’s API. In addition, their smart contracts actively include information about how the state will be mapped into the relational database, which distorts the purpose of DLT transactions and would force to adapt all other systems that should interact with that DLT network.

b) **The target database.** Relational databases are a common choice since they are by far the most established and feature efficient indexing mechanisms and query language (the SQL standard). Some systems that synchronize the state of a DLT into a relational database are Vent [27], Ledgerdata Refiner [28] and ChainSQL [29]. Although this approach makes it possible to provide efficient query interfaces, its main disadvantage is the fact that the state data structure must be known beforehand since it is needed to create the database tables. A particular exception is the case of Ledgerdata Refiner, but at the expense of having to parse the state in every single query (due to the aforementioned disadvantages in the state storage format), unless the query execution engine is combined with a text analysis tool. Other proposals opt for document-oriented databases (observe these are not key-value databases such as LevelDB). BigchainDB [23] chooses MongoDB, while LedgerSync [26] chooses RethinkDB. This approach’s main

advantage is that it allows to deal with schema-free documents, which makes updating the database state from the DLT state to be straightforward, since there is no need to restructure the state data in the process. Its possible disadvantages are that queries could not be as efficient as in relational databases (when they involve some of the document’s inner fields instead of the indexing keys). In addition, they do not provide a common language as SQL, thus forcing the user to commit to the specific query language of each database provider.

c) **The synchronization mechanisms.** LedgerSync [26] uses the events emitted from the DLT node when committing a block of transactions as its single source of data for getting updates from the ledger state. This could become troublesome when missing an event’s reception or in case the node already contains committed information that the database lacks at the moment of launching the tool and establishing the subscription. Vent [27] and Ledgerdata Refiner [28] provide crash fault tolerance. They explicitly query for the last block committed, comparing it with the last block number stored in the database, retrieving those blocks that were not yet persisted. This approach corrects the deficiencies of the strategy outlined by LedgerSync. Ledgerdata Refiner relies only on periodic queries to every node every two seconds, while Vent mainly relies on the reception of events from the DLT, but it also includes mechanisms for detecting missing blocks, which will be retrieved straightaway from the node itself.

There seems to be, thus, a clear shortcoming in the support of complex data states, as existing solutions directed to address this issue, actually propose either a potentially inefficient approach for query execution [28] or a design that complicates the integration with other systems [29].

III. OVERVIEW

DELTA’s purpose is to facilitate the interaction with DLTs for developers and users. This is achieved through the development of a software solution that enables the easy execution of read operations on a distributed ledger, supporting efficient queries on data states with a complex structure. In addition, this solution includes mechanisms acting as Simplified Payment Verification (SPV), which makes it feasible to match the data assets in the database to their related DLT transactions, thus verifying their authenticity.

DELTA specifies an implementation model that allows to transparently plug in different DLTs and databases in an interchangeable fashion. This is achieved by generalizing and abstracting the specification of the operations that DLTs and databases need to provide. Integrating a particular DLT (or database) will then require the development of a driver implementing the operations of this abstract specification. Some of the most relevant interfaces and methods to implement when designing a DLT or Database driver are listed in Table I, with special emphasis in `IDeltaClient` and `IDeltaDatabaseConnector`.

The adoption of a component-oriented approach enables the encapsulation of algorithms and common behavior patterns into well defined components, contributing to code reuse,

Fig. 1. Interrelationship between the conceptual areas composing the synchronization tool.

ease of debugging and maintenance. These components are independent of the underlying technologies, operating on top of the abstract operation interfaces already mentioned, which are implemented by technology-specific drivers. Examples of components are a block explorer (which checks the network progress in terms of blocks and transactions, and either logs out this information or inserts it into a database), a smart contract resolver (notifies when an unidentified smart contract is detected to be submitting transactions to the DLT), and a code event subscriber (subscribes to events emitted from a smart contract and performs an action upon their reception). Applications are conceived as an assembly of high-level components (which can integrate other lower-level components) and act as selector wrappers that link the components instantiated to the chosen technologies. An example of this would be an application that initializes the HLF and MongoDB connectors, instantiates the block explorer component, supplying it with the connectors, and launches the component.

Presently, DELTA comes with implementations for HLF and Quorum, both popular choices, well established in the area of permissioned DLTs. DELTA also comes with an implementation for MongoDB, also a widely used, well established, and popular document database. Since smart contracts usually store their state as JSON resources, the choice of a document oriented database is a good match for a DLT-DB replication, avoiding the need to perform transformations on the data structure of an asset. Document databases are not required, however, in DELTA. DELTA’s flexible design allows integrating other database technologies, such as relational databases. Again, supporting any other DLT or database just requires the development of a driver implementing the corresponding operation interface (mainly, `IDeltaClient` or `IDeltaDatabaseConnector`) for that technology. Components and applications developed for DELTA would need no modification whatsoever. Figure 1 presents a diagram with the interrelationship between the conceptual areas encompassing the entities introduced to this point.

Table II compares DELTA with some of the approaches that we presented in Section II in terms of their coverage of five different aspects of synchronization, namely: storage of complex assets, efficient queries on complex assets, crash fault recovery, support to multiple DLTs, and support to multiple databases. This aims to display a qualitative measure of the completeness of such approaches and highlight their strong and weak points. DELTA fulfills these aspects, overcoming the shortcomings of previous systems.

TABLE I
MAIN INTERFACES REQUIRED TO IMPLEMENT A DRIVER FOR A DLT OR A DATABASE.

DLT Driver interfaces		Database Driver interfaces	
IDeltaClient		IDeltaDatabaseConnector	
query	subscribeToBlockEvents	connect	createAsset
invokeSync	subscribeToCodeEvents	disconnect	updateAsset
invokeAsync	disconnectEventHub	storeBlock	upsertAsset
replayBlockEvents	instantiateSmartContract	addTransactionsToBlock	deleteAsset
replayCodeEvents	detectNewSmartContracts	getBlock	retrieveAsset
Other DLT interfaces		getBlockFromTransaction	retrieveAllAssets
		getLastBlock	getLastTransaction
		getAllBlocks	getAllTransactions
		executeQuery	querySynchronizedSmartContracts
		SmartContract	BlockEvent
ContractEvent	Transaction		

TABLE II
SUPPORT OF SYNCHRONIZATION FEATURES BY THE TECHNOLOGIES ANALYZED, COMPARED TO DELTA

	Storage of complex assets	Efficient queries on complex assets	Crash fault recovery	Multiple DLT technologies	Multiple DB technologies
BigchainDB [23]	✓	✓	✓	✗*	✗
Blockchain Relational Database [24]	✓	✓	✓	✗*	✗
LedgerSync [26]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Vent [27]	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
Ledgerdata Refiner [28]	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
ChainSQL [29]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
DELTA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

*Implements its own DLT, instead of coupling to a node in a network of a previously existing technology.

IV. HIGH LEVEL DESIGN

In this Section we describe the inner details of DELTA. First, we present the synchronization strategy, that uses event emission from the DLT along with event reception and processing by the client application. Next, we describe the custom smart contracts that broadcast these events, highlighting how they extend the data modification primitives of basic smart contracts. Finally, we introduce some advanced techniques for synchronization, such as the crash fault tolerance mechanisms, which enable the application to recover from crashes, and the dynamic subscription model, which gets the application automatically subscribed to events from new smart contracts as soon as they start committing transactions into the ledger.

A. Event synchronization strategy

The synchronization of the ledger contents into a database is based on the broadcast of events from the DLT network nodes when applying committed transactions. DELTA operates as a client application which connects to one of the nodes in the network and keeps listening to events broadcast from that node. These events can be block or code events. The former are automatically broadcast when the node receives a new transaction block that has been approved by the consensus algorithm. The latter originate from event emission instructions included in the smart contract code by its developer, and are broadcast as the node applies in its ledger replica the transaction comprising these events. Code events are a part of the transaction, since they are generated from the smart contract execution, along with data read and write operations. The

subscription to block and code events is enabled by calls to the `subscribeToBlockEvents` and `subscribeToCodeEvents` methods, respectively, in the `IDeltaClient` interface.

Block events include data such as block number, block hash and the identifiers of the transactions contained in the block. DELTA holds a subscription to new block events, in order to keep a global persistent registry of the blocks received and the transactions contained within. This feature, in addition to allowing to check the network's progress in terms of transaction blocks committed, works as a reverse cache to determine the block each transaction belongs to. This facilitates the query of individual transactions directly on the DLT nodes and becomes very useful for performing accountability tasks.

The emission of code events is defined in smart contracts by the inclusion of specific instructions, so that these events are broadcast (bound to the smart contract and transaction identifiers) when the node applies the corresponding transaction. DELTA creates a listener for each smart contract the application gets subscribed to, managing the subscription to each smart contract in an independent execution thread.

These code events are used in DELTA to synchronize the ledger state into the database. For this, a specification of the format to be followed by code events has been defined, according to CRUD operation semantics. Every time a smart contract executes a data modification operation over the ledger state, it emits an event into which such an operation is encoded. When the client application receives the event, DELTA processes it according to the code event specification and applies the

```

interface DeltaEvent {
  // Event specification version number
  delta: string,
  // [CREATE, UPDATE, DELETE]
  operation: DeltaOperation,
  data: {
    // Key
    key: string,
    // Value. Optional, only for CREATE|UPDATE
    asset: any
  }
}

```

Listing 1. DELTA event structure

corresponding data modification operation on the database (createAsset, updateAsset, or deleteAsset, as defined by the IDeltaDatabaseConnector interface). This way, the database contents are kept in sync with the ledger as long as code events are received, processed, and applied, meeting the rules of eventual data consistency.

B. Smart contracts

DELTA requires that, every time a data modification operation is executed in the smart contract code, an event that encodes the operation according to the DELTA’s event specification format is emitted. Nevertheless, it would not be acceptable to compel smart contract developers who wish to benefit from DELTA’s advantages to get familiar with the specification and explicitly build and emit those events. In order to avoid this issue, a base smart contract is provided for both HLF (TypeScript) and Quorum (Solidity), supplying the protected (in terms of function visibility) implementation of a CRUD interface. Each of this interface’s data modification operations receives a couple of parameters sticking to key-value semantics, from which the operation is executed on the smart contract’s persistent state and the corresponding event is built and emitted, matching DELTA’s event specification. This enables smart contract developers to make their own contracts extend from this parent contract by means of inheritance mechanisms and get DELTA’s benefits, just calling operations provided by the base smart contract instead of native data modification primitives. Of course, smart contract developers can always avoid inheritance from the base smart contract provided and manually implement data modification operations along with event construction and emission.

DELTA’s event specification establishes that events must contain a (serialized) JSON document with a fixed structure, shown in Listing 1 as a TypeScript interface. The asset field contains the value bound to the key provided in the smart contract persistent state. Although this field can be an instance of any data type, it will usually be a nested JSON document.

C. Advanced synchronization mechanisms

A key aspect of DELTA’s design is the ability of the synchronization tool to recover from failures, as well as the type of failures the application can recover from. DELTA’s design and implementation have been conceived in such a way that it keeps a registry of the smart contracts it is syncing and the index of the last block synchronized for each one of

them, which works as a set of counters. This information is stored in the local database and can be retrieved by calling the querySynchronizedSmartContracts and getLastBlock methods in the IDeltaDatabaseConnector interface. Therefore, upon events like an application reboot or a temporary connection loss, the application can resume the synchronization process at the point it was before the interruption happened, receiving every event emitted from the last block synchronized for each smart contract. The mechanisms designed for this ensure that no transaction blocks are missed and that all transactions are applied to the corresponding smart contracts, according to the order determined by the network’s consensus algorithm.

Moreover, after a shutdown period during which the network kept committing transaction blocks, these fault tolerance mechanisms allow the application to restart the previous subscription, request every transaction block that could have been missed, process it and get up to date with the ledger most recent status. An edge case is that of having lost the whole local database (or synchronizing over a fresh database and a DLT network that has already been running for a while); in this scenario the mechanisms aforementioned will perform a complete recovery, making the database reach the ledger’s current status by getting and applying sequentially every transaction committed since the network originated.

Another topic that is also addressed by DELTA is how to determine which smart contracts, of all those deployed in the DLT network, must be synchronized into the database. Since it is actually a decision that depends mostly on the user’s context and purpose, DELTA provides two modes of subscription to smart contracts. The first option is to allow the user to provide the identifiers of the smart contracts to be synchronized, denoted as fixed subscription model. The second option is to enable dynamic smart contract resolution, by means of the detectNewSmartContracts method in the IDeltaClient interface. This second mechanism starts a new subscription every time a new transaction originates in a smart contract for which no active subscriptions exist. In this case, every smart contract in the DLT network will eventually get synchronized without the user being required to specify any of their identifiers. These two subscription modes are not mutually exclusive, since the user can set a fixed subscription to some smart contracts and, in addition, enable dynamic resolution in order to get subscribed to those smart contracts that, while being previously unregistered, commit transactions since the point in time when the synchronization was started or resumed.

It is important to note that the mechanisms used for dynamic smart contract resolution entail an overload in computational and temporal terms, since, for every transaction block received, they need to perform an explicit query to the node in order to retrieve the whole block contents, analyze each transaction to find out the smart contract having submitted it, and verify whether an active subscription to that smart contract already exists or a new subscription must be launched. We measure this overhead, jointly with the time required to synchronize a

DLT and a database, in Section V. Another potential disadvantage of indiscriminately making use of this smart contract resolution mechanism, without a proper assessment, is that the whole network ledger status will be synchronized, instead of the state of just a specific set of smart contracts. This fact could lead to store in the local database a higher than desired volume of data, in case the DLT network holds a high amount of deployed active smart contracts.

V. EVALUATION

In this section we assess DELTA in order to evaluate different aspects of its performance. First, we measure the overhead and time required to synchronize a DLT with a database in the worst case scenario, i.e., having to synchronize all the assets in the ledger. Secondly, we estimate the improvements in terms of query efficiency that can be achieved with a solution of this kind. To do so, we evaluate DELTA in two different scenarios: executing key-value and complex queries, with three different types of assets and with both HLF and Quorum as DLTs.

A. Experimental setup

All experiments have been executed on a DLT network of seven nodes, for both HLF and Quorum, selecting Raft as consensus algorithm. Each node is placed in a different virtual machine, running Ubuntu 20.04.2 and comprising 4 vCPUs of 2GHz each, 8GB RAM and 50GB HDD. The client application executing the tests is a Node v12.22.10 process running in another virtual machine with equal specifications and deployed in the same VLAN as the DLT nodes.

For both technologies, HLF and Quorum, we used three different types of JSON documents with increasingly complex structure and size: small (0.3KB, no nesting), medium (2KB, 2 nesting levels) and large (18KB, 4 nesting levels). Both factors, document size and the complexity of its structure, became relevant when executing queries on them.

B. DELTA's overhead and synchronization time

Section IV mentioned that our solution introduces an overhead when it is updating a database to the contents of the DLT, as DELTA must process and validate all events received from a DLT node, and prepare them to get inserted in the database. Similarly, we also mentioned that DELTA can recover from errors such as shutdown periods or loss of the database, although this introduces a delay due to the re-synchronization. We measured both aspects assuming the worst case scenario, i.e., losing the database and having to synchronize it completely.

We found that the overhead depends on the DLT we are synchronizing with and its event model. For HLF, events are emitted as JSON documents and their processing overhead is negligible (for instance, event processing only demanded 179ms out of 72787ms for database insertions in the worst case, when 40000 large assets had been handled). This, however, was not the case for Quorum, where the overhead was more significant, as we show in Figure 2. This figure stacks event processing time and database insertion time

Fig. 2. Latency in DELTA's asset synchronization per volume of Quorum documents stored, differentiating between event processing and database insertion. Syncing with a DLT with 40000 large assets takes less than 90 seconds ($\sim 2ms/asset$), while inserting them in the DLT took around 50 minutes.

when synchronizing data from a Quorum node for different combinations of number of assets and asset size. The reason for this - perceptible - overhead is that, in Quorum, events must be reconstructed, requiring the explicit decoding of complex data types, which is a time consuming process. However, our aggregated transaction dispatching rate in this (worst) case scenario is still much higher than when emitting transactions to any of the two DLTs tested, according to the experiments run. For instance, as we can observe in Figure 2, we could sync 40000 large assets in less than 90 seconds, i.e., less than 2ms per asset, while inserting them in the DLT took around 50 minutes¹.

C. Key-value queries

In this first scenario, we evaluate the cost of performing key-value queries, i.e., retrieving an asset from its identifier or indexing key. Figure 3(a) displays the median times for the execution of 200 random key-value queries, repeated as the ledger/database size increases, for the three technologies compared (HLF, Quorum, and MongoDB) and for each of the three types of document presented. MongoDB times keep almost constant for these key-value queries, regardless of the number of documents stored or their volume and its performance is, by large, superior to that of Quorum or HLF. Quorum is between two and five times slower than MongoDB, except for large assets, where its performance decays with the ledger size, being one order of magnitude worse than MongoDB in this experiment. HLF, although not much affected by the asset size, can become almost three orders of magnitude slower than MongoDB as the ledger grows.

The adjacent plot in Figure 3(b) shows the dispersion in the recurring execution of these queries, for HLF and Quorum, grouped by the document type and the ledger size. While dispersion in Quorum is limited, in HLF it is quite relevant, specially as the number of assets stored increases. We did not include the dispersion for MongoDB as it was negligible.

Both latency and dispersion are higher in HLF than in Quorum. Key-value asset retrieval in HLF requires querying the

¹We do not provide figures or details on the insertion of data in the DLT due to space limitations.

(a) Median times for key-value queries.

(b) Query time dispersion in HLF and Quorum.

Fig. 3. (a) MongoDB times remain almost constant for key-value queries, regardless of the number of documents stored or their volume. Quorum is between two and five times slower than MongoDB, except for large assets, where its performance decays with the ledger size, being one order of magnitude worse than MongoDB. HLF, although not much affected by the asset size, can become almost three orders of magnitude slower than MongoDB as the ledger grows. (b) While dispersion in Quorum is limited, in HLF it is quite relevant, specially as the number of assets stored increases.

underlying CouchDB from the smart contract. Quorum implements this operation by directly extracting the corresponding value from a Solidity mapping (a data structure describing a hash-map), although the smart contract’s state is still stored in an underlying LevelDB that would need to be queried anyway. The results observed may imply either that the submission of read-only calls to smart contracts is faster in Quorum than in HLF, that Quorum’s internal data structures are better than HLF’s for key-value asset retrieval, that LevelDB is faster and more timely consistent than CouchDB for such operations, or that the database connector used by Quorum is noticeably more performant than the one used by HLF.

D. Complex queries

In the second scenario, we evaluate the cost of performing complex queries. By complex queries we refer to the retrieval of all assets matching specific filtering criteria, an intricate expression composed of multiple custom conditions. HLF splits into raw and enhanced queries. The latter take advantage from the capabilities of HLF’s smart contracts to execute queries via the API of CouchDB when it is the database supporting the ledger, while the former are implemented by linearly traversing all assets stored in the smart contract’s data state, applying the filtering criteria to them and keeping those that match the comparison. Since Solidity does not provide facilities for querying, we implemented a query mechanism on Quorum’s smart contracts that imitates HLF’s raw queries.

Figure 4(a) displays the median times for the execution of 20 complex queries, repeated as the ledger/database size increases, for the three technologies compared and each of the three types of document contemplated. For these queries, MongoDB latency increases with the database size independently of the documents’ complexity and volume and, as expected, outperforms both HLF and Quorum. HLF queries

follow a similar trend, although times are between one (enhanced queries) and two (raw queries) orders of magnitude worse. Quorum query times are substantially higher and its performance decays faster, resulting in query times that were between 2 and 5 orders of magnitude higher than for MongoDB. Observe that we could only run queries for up to 8000 and 24000 assets for the large and medium asset types, respectively. Beyond these volumes, the Geth processes running on the Quorum nodes started throwing timeouts and aborting the running query. If we had been able to execute queries for larger volumes of assets, this difference would have gone beyond 5 orders of magnitude.

Figure 4(b) shows the dispersion in HLF queries, grouped by asset type and for different amounts of assets in the ledger, and differentiating between raw and enhanced queries. Dispersion here remained controlled but became relevant for the 40K assets sample. This difference is due to the higher efficiency of CouchDB, that reduced the impact of the asset size on the enhanced queries. The nesting in the large asset did affect the raw queries severely. Figure 4(c) shows the dispersion in Quorum queries, which, on the other hand, is severely affected by the asset complexity, i.e., the nesting and volume. As in the key-value case, dispersion in MongoDB queries was negligible and it is not displayed.

As opposed to key-value queries, complex queries are far slower and their latencies are more sparse in Quorum than in HLF. While HLF’s queries (both raw and enhanced) could be successfully executed for this experiment, Quorum queries did not even complete for documents more complex than the small asset. The brute-force approach of complex queries in Quorum greatly penalizes its performance, especially when compared to the enhanced queries of HLF on top of CouchDB. However, HLF’s implementation of raw queries is actually similar to Quorum’s, but the former are way faster than the

Fig. 4. (a) MongoDB complex query latency increases with the database size independently of the assets’ complexity. HLF queries follow a similar trend, although times are between one and two orders of magnitude worse. Quorum query times are substantially higher and performance decays faster, being 5 orders of magnitude slower than MongoDB. (b) Dispersion in HLF complex queries remained controlled but became relevant for the 40K assets sample and raw queries, which did not cope well with nested documents. (c) On the other hand, dispersion in Quorum is severely affected by the asset complexity.

latter; even if they are one order of magnitude slower than HLF’s enhanced queries, and their dispersion is also greater when the asset complexity and the document size increase. The significant performance difference between raw queries on HLF and Quorum could be just a consequence of how the operations they make use of (looping, data selection, retrieval and decoding, and value comparison) are internally built in the smart contract execution runtime of each platform. A specific profiling process would be required to assess this reasoning.

VI. DISCUSSION

Our solution intends to mitigate DLT’s limitations related to data retrieval, by adding a synchronized local database. It must be noted that, nevertheless, restrictions of the underlying DLT related to transaction throughput and the deterioration of its performance as the ledger size grows still apply. Therefore, our solution does not enable the adoption of DLTs on inappropriate use cases, where such restrictions are not admissible.

DELTA’s synchronization is based on the subscription to events emitted from smart contracts, since it is provided by most current mainstream DLTs. Relying upon event emission implies that the integration of a DLT whose smart contracts do not feature this mechanism would require a rework in DELTA’s core, in order to enable an alternative procedure for synchronization.

Smart contracts also require to define the encoding and emission of events matching DELTA’s specification whenever an operation involving persistent data modification is executed. DELTA provides base contracts including implementations of these operations for every technology currently supported. However, in case the DLT does not support contract upgrade, smart contracts would still require to be DELTA-conformant at the moment they are first deployed. Currently, DELTA smart contracts do not provide information about their data model, since the synchronization is performed on a schema-free database (MongoDB). In case a structured (e.g., relational) database is adopted, this information should be made available. The most straightforward option is embedding information

about the data model in the contract’s code and enable its retrieval via an additional read-only public method.

Finally, the local database itself does not hold any guarantees related to data integrity. Its purpose is to boost queries, but the DLT must still be checked in case of data auditing. To this end, every asset stored in the database contains the identifier of the corresponding transaction, so that they can be traced back to the DLT to verify their validity.

VII. CONCLUSION

DELTA provides a tool to synchronize the state of a DLT on a local database with negligible overhead, thus enabling the operation with smart contracts whose data states possess a complex structure. It facilitates the execution of complex queries on that shared state, kept by the nodes hosting replicas of the ledger. Query times decrease, at least, between one and five orders of magnitude, depending on the DLT, compared to queries directed to the ledger nodes.

This solution is an improvement upon previously existing approaches, providing additional useful features. Examples of such innovative features are the ability to recover and resume the synchronization process upon crashes or network interruptions, as well as the dynamic identification of smart contracts deployed on the network, enabling the automatic synchronization of their contents. Its architecture is based on a modular approach, agnostic to specific technology implementation details, thus supporting multiple DLTs and databases and easing the adoption of new technologies on both scopes. The current release of DELTA includes the implementation of drivers for Hyperledger Fabric, Quorum, and MongoDB.

Since DELTA enables DLTs to be queried by using database languages and semantics, potential future research lines include complementing this effort with the ability to write on DLTs (actually, submit transactions) by means of similar mechanisms, thus further simplifying adoption of DLTs, supplying them with a complete database-like interaction model that, moreover, supports the efficient execution of complex custom queries.

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